

PERCEPTION OF HEADTEACHERS' SERVANT LEADERSHIP STYLE AS LEEWAY OF MITIGATING CORRUPT PRACTICES AMONG PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examined the perception of Headteachers' servant leadership styles as leeway for mitigating corrupt practices among Lagos State, Nigeria primary school teachers. Corruption is a form of dishonest and unethical behaviour orchestrated by a person trusted in a position. It is ubiquitous and spread to every sector including education. In Lagos State primary school environment where corrupt practice poses a serious challenge to academic excellence, the Headteachers need a servant leadership style to sustain ethical standards and academic integrity. Corrupt practices of some primary school teachers include embezzlement of school fund; selling of school properties; extortion from pupils, forgery of certificates; falsification of school records; sexual harassment with pupils and so on. This clarion call necessitates the importance of servant leadership approach to cushion the effect of corruption which has bedeviled both public and private primary school systems in Lagos State, Nigeria. Servant leadership is a philosophical approach of leaders who belief in serving followers above all other priorities. The Headteachers' servant leadership style in primary school warrants fostering a culture of integrity, trust, empathy, stewardship, humility, honesty, transparency, accountability, listening, commitment and community engagement toward achieving educational objectives. These necessitate the importance of a Headteacher's servant leadership style in creating a positive, supportive and dynamic work environment for primary school teachers in Lagos State to reduce the likelihood of engaging in corrupt practices. The study concludes that head teachers who observed corrupt practices among teachers in primary schools need to adopt a servant leadership style and prepare for sacrifice with a supportive culture of being transparent, accountable, humble and encourages teachers to perform their academic work without lethargy to attainment of educational objectives. The study recommended government should implement and foster for servant leadership style in public primary schools to curb teacher's corrupt practices and improve the quality of primary education in Lagos State as reflected in the national policy on Education.

Keywords: Corrupt Practices, Head-Teacher, Servant Leadership and Teacher

Introduction

Education appears to be generally acknowledged as the most viable tool for sustaining socio-economic, political and national development. National Policy on Education (2013) clearly defines Nigeria's educational goals for personal and national development. Education can be

formal, semi- formal, or informal. Formal education is divided into primary, secondary, and postsecondary levels. The primary school system serves as the foundation for future learning and is very important in the lives of the students. The goal of primary education in the National Policy on Education is to instill permanent reading and numeracy in pupils, as well as to inculcate in them a variety of basic knowledge and abilities for further educational advancement, such as correct values and morals. However, these laudable objectives could be actualized if the leadership of primary education is effective and efficient. Leadership seems to be a systematic process by which a superior influence, persuades, convinces and inspire followers to achieve organisational goals and objectives. According to Mohammed, Shittu and Lawal (2019), leadership is an essential element in any human organization. As management is the heart of formal organization, leadership is the soul of management.

However, the success of formal organization observed to depends on the leadership styles of its leaders. Leadership seems to be process by which a superior person influences subordinates to work toward the actualization of organizational goals and objectives. In the primary school system, leadership started with the headteachers who oversee operation and implementation of teaching and learning activities. at the helm of affairs in primary schools. The headteacher is tasked with giving guidance and leadership gravitas that will not only help primary school teachers to become more focused but also utilize their shown skills, making them a well-known classroom manager.

Leadership is the ability of a superior officer to influence the behaviour of a follower or subordinate to accomplish educational goals and objectives. According to Kamugisha (2013), leadership is a noteworthy manner by which one changes the minds of followers and steer to achieve set objectives. However, leadership style is therefore the typical way of behaviour exhibited by a leader. Leadership styles could be in different fora which includes autocratic leadership style, democratic leadership style, laissez-faire leadership style, transformational leadership style, transactional leadership style, servant leadership style and so on.

Moreover, servant leadership refers to a leadership style that focuses on serving followers, prioritizing their needs and empowering them to accomplish their goals and objectives in an organisation. Servant leaders prioritize the needs of others, share authority, responsibility, and power, and support their growth and performance. Servant leadership is a choice made by the individual to serve rather than occupy a leadership position (Iyer, 2013). Servant leader tend

to prioritize the needs, interests and aspirations of the people they lead at the top (Rau, et. al. 2015). There are five dimensions in servant leadership: love, empowerment, trust, humility and vision (Tomigolung, 2015). Servant leadership emphasizes the growth of the follower to achieve organizational objectives. By adopting a servant leadership approach, primary schools can promote a culture of transparency, accountability, and integrity, ultimately reducing the risk of corruption.

Perspective of Servant Leadership Style

The origin of the term “Servant Leadership” is accredited to Greenleaf who in 1970 published an essay titled, “The servant as leader”, after he reviews of a novel, ‘Journey to the East’ by Herman Hesse in 1960. He thinks that a great leader must first become a servant and get the experience as the servant, which is central to his/her greatness. Greenleaf (1970) explained that “The Servant- Leader is servant first. It begins with a natural feeling that one wants to serve first. Then conscious choice brings one to aspire to lead. Greenleaf further proposed that Servant Leadership is a leadership process in which there is a genuine concern of the leader towards the follower. This concern therefore, brings about serving and leading the followers at the same time. Moreover, servant leadership is a type of leadership that encourages people to work together. A leader intends to help the institution’s personnel favorably. The school leader interacts with teachers and administrative staff as a collegial friend rather than a boss and tries to make things as easy as possible for them. Servant leadership is a useful leadership approach for educational organizations whose main function is to improve the qualities of people (Taylor, Martin, Hutchinson & Jinks, 2007). Greenleaf generally agree that the following behaviour are central to the development of a servant- leader:

1. Listening: Greenleaf argued that the first response of a genuine servant leader is to listen to the followers. It is also argued that listening enhances open communication and could lead to employee’s increased motivation, high trust, more care, lower absenteeism and the reduction of vices within the organisation (Stone, Russell and Patterson, 2004; Flynn, Smither and Walker, 2008). Therefore, it can be confirmed that listening is a key characteristic of servant leadership. Headteachers need to be reinforced by a deep commitment to listening intently to others.
2. Empathy: Empathy is the ability of a leader to align with a follower’s situation to comprehend their position and perspective. Servant-leaders try to empathize with and understand others' feelings and emotions. It is assumed that an individual has good intentions even when he or she performs poorly. Workers may be considered not only as employees, but also as people

who need respect and appreciation for their personal development.

3. Emotional Healing: Emotional healing signifies a leader's ability and zeal to encourage followers' recovery from difficulties. McCann, Grave and Cox (2014) found that within organisations, there would always be the need for followers and even leaders to recover from personal hardships or trauma. They stated that the servant leader's use of effective listening and empathy facilitates the healing process and enhances the relationship between the servant leader and the follower.
4. Awareness: Awareness is the ability of servant leaders to be conscious of self and general activities around them. He further argued that awareness would strengthen the leader's interaction with followers ethically. Servant-leaders are very self-aware of their strengths and weaknesses. Pavlovich and Corner (2015), they extend further by categorising the awareness of a servant leader into two types:
 - i. Self- awareness: This connotes a sense that the servant leader is conscious of self as an individual entity within the environment and is still mindful of their interrelationship with the environment.
 - ii. External-awareness: This extends the view of self-awareness and indicates that the servant leader's conscious awareness of self now equips them with the ability to connect their awareness with those of followers.
5. Persuasion: Persuasion as a characteristic that the servant leader depends upon in decision-making, rather than exerting the use of authority. He argued that the servant leader seeks to convince and obtain commitment from followers rather than force compliance. Servant-leaders do not take advantage of their power and status by coercing compliance; instead, they try to convince those they manage. The servant-leader is therefore effective at building consensus within groups.
6. Conceptualization: Conceptualization as the ability of the servant leader to "dream great dreams", and think beyond the status quo for effective leadership. Servant-leaders take the time and effort to develop a desirable vision of the future. That means they can see beyond the current activities of the operating organisation and can focus on long term goals.
7. Foresight: Foresight is the ability to anticipate the likely outcome of a course of action or a situation. This foresight also enables the servant leader to identify the consequences of the future, a characteristic closely related to conceptualization.
8. Growth: Servant leaders are committed to the growth of their followers because they see their followers as having an intrinsic value beyond their contributions as workers. He argued that a great outcome of the practice of servant leadership is the development of followers in a positive

way, which he identified as growth. Servant-leaders are committed to people beyond their immediate work role. They commit to fostering an environment that encourages the personal and professional growth of their followers and employees.

9. **Community Building:** Community building signifies the leader's capacity to encourage a sense of community spirit within the organisation. According to Spears (2010), servant leaders have a sense of duty to build community among those who work within the organisation, yet also the larger society.

Corrupt Practices Among Primary School Teachers in Lagos State

Corruption in primary schools seems to manifest in various ways, undermining the integrity of the education system and compromising students' learning experience. The following are examples of how corruption can manifest in primary schools: Illegal charges levied on children's school admission forms which are supposed to be free; children from certain communities favoured for admission, others subjected to extra payments; good grades and exam pass obtained through bribes to teachers and public officials. The prices are often well known, and candidates can be expected to pay up-front; removing the consequences of failing exams by (re-)admitting students under false names; embezzlement of funds intended for teaching materials and school buildings; sub-standard educational material purchased due to manufacturers' bribes; schools monopolising meals and uniforms, resulting in low quality and high prices; private tutoring outside school hours given to paying pupils, reducing teachers' motivation in ordinary classes, and reserving compulsory topics for the private sessions to the detriment of other pupils; school property used for private commercial purposes; pupils carrying out unpaid labour for the benefit of the staff; staff exploit and abuse pupils in many ways (physically, sexually); teacher recruitment and postings influenced by bribes or sexual favours; exam questions sold in advance; ghost teachers – salaries drawn for staff who are no longer (or never were) employed for various reasons (including having passed away); high absenteeism, with severe effects on de facto student-teacher ratio; licenses and authorisations for teaching obtained on false grounds via corrupt means; inflated student numbers (including numbers of special-needs pupils) quoted to obtain better funding; bribes to auditors for not disclosing the misuse of funds; embezzlement of funds raised by local NGOs and parents' organisations; some politicians allocating resources to particular schools to gain support, especially during election times.

Servant Leadership and Teachers Corrupt Practices in Primary School

In the primary school system, particularly in Lagos State, Nigeria. Servant leadership becomes relevant for headteachers to tackle the menace of corruption which is rampant among teaching staff due to poor conditions of service, low wages and salary structure, inadequate professional training, pressure to perform and inadequate school funding. This ugly situation orchestrated some public primary school teachers to engaged in bribery, favoritism, examination malpractices, embezzlement of funds, stealing of school properties and so on. Today, headteacher servant leadership style seems to be necessary to mitigate corrupt practices among teachers and academic integrity in the primary school system because corruption has become general phenomenon which has pose serious challenges to primary school in Lagos State, Nigeria. However, corruption occurs when someone in a position of power uses their authority to influence decisions or conducts any other dishonest or fraudulent behaviour. Primary school teachers are not immune to corrupt practices, which can undermine the quality of education. Corrupt practices orchestrated by some primary school teachers include embezzlement of school funds; selling of school properties; extortion from pupils, forgery of certificates; falsification of school records; sexual harassment of pupils and so on. This clarion call necessitates the importance of servant leadership approach to cushion the effect of corruption which has bedeviled primary schools' system in Lagos State, Nigeria. The headteachers' servant leadership style in primary schools warrant a fostering culture of integrity, trust, empathy, stewardship, humility, honesty, transparency, accountability, listening, commitment and community engagement toward achieving educational objectives. These necessitate the importance of Headteacher's servant leadership style in creating a positive, supportive and dynamic work environment for primary school teachers in Lagos State to reduce the likelihood of engaging in corrupt practices. Servant leadership has been identified as a leadership style that can promote ethical behavior and mitigate corruption.

Panacea for Servant Leadership to Mitigating Corrupt Practices in Primary School

Servant leadership is a leadership philosophy that primary school head prioritizes the needs of teachers, fosters a culture of trust and accountability, and promotes ethical decision-making.

The

following are some ways to mitigate teachers corrupt practices by headteacher servant leadership approach:

1. Fostering a Culture of Transparency and Accountability

- Lead by example: Demonstrate transparency and accountability in your own actions and decisions.

- Encourage open communication: Foster an environment where individuals feel comfortable reporting concerns or suspicions of corruption.
- Establish clear policies and procedures: Develop and communicate clear policies and procedures that promote transparency and accountability.

2. Empowering Others to Prevent Corruption

- Provide training and education: Offer training and education on corruption prevention, ethics, and integrity.
- Encourage whistleblower reporting: Establish a safe and confidential reporting mechanism for individuals to report suspected corruption.
- Foster a culture of peer accountability: Encourage individuals to hold each other accountable for promoting a culture of integrity.

3. Building Trust and Credibility

- Demonstrate empathy and compassion: Show understanding and empathy towards individuals who may be struggling with corruption-related issues.
- Foster a culture of trust: Encourage open communication, transparency, and accountability to build trust among stakeholders in education.
- Lead with integrity: Demonstrate integrity in your own actions and decisions to promote a culture of integrity within the school settings.

Implication

By implication, this study suggests servant leadership styles can be suitable for headteachers as a leeway of mitigating corrupt practices among primary school teachers in Lagos State, Nigeria. Servant leaders inspire their subordinates and care for them. This presupposes that headteacher who adopted servant leadership style need to respect and inspire their teachers to achieve their professional objectives. In terms of cordial relationships, the headteacher can build a healthy working environment to encourage teamwork. Headteachers who demonstrate servant leadership characteristics can foster a positive school culture, promote ethical behaviour, and reduce the incidence of corrupt practices. By promoting servant leadership, schools can create a positive and ethical learning environment that supports the academic and personal growth of students. This position is in line with Ajayi (2022) maintains that a cursory look at some primary schools in Nigeria shows that some of the major problems faced by these

schools could be traced to the poor leadership competence of headteachers, which contributed to corrupt practices in school system.

Conclusion

Headteachers serve as leaders in the school, develop and lead teachers appropriately. The leadership style of a school leader, specifically Headteachers, can help to mitigate corrupt practices among teachers. Servant leadership is a well-known leadership style in the business and organizational psychology field but has applications in the education setting as well. This entails how Headteachers can be servant-leaders by putting others first and themselves second. As a result, it enhances team growth. Therefore, educators need to learn how Headteachers can most effectively lead teachers and other support staff. Training and professional development opportunities are essential for school leaders to learn how to be supportive and equitable when working with others.

Recommendations

The study recommended the following:

1. State government should continue to provide headteacher training and development programs to enhance their servant leadership skills and professional integrity on periodic basis.
2. The government should foster servant leadership style in public primary schools to mitigate teacher's corrupt practices and improve the quality of primary education in Lagos State as reflected in the National Policy on Education.
3. The ministry of Education should organised seminars and conferences to promote a culture of transparency, accountability, and ethical behaviour among professional teachers in Lagos State.
4. Headteachers should encourage teachers to report any corrupt practices in the school system and provided with protection for the whistleblowers.
5. The government should establish clear policies and procedures for addressing corrupt practices among parents, teachers, and school administrators which can affect pupil learning and well-being.
6. Conduct regular audits and monitoring to review financial transactions, procurement processes, and other areas prone to corruption.
7. Headteacher should implement anti-corruption policies to prevent corruption among teachers such as conflict-of-interest policies and gift policies.

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